

Clean Air – Need of the Hour for A Healthier India

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ABSTRACT

Air pollution levels in India are among the highest in the world, posing a significant threat to the country's health and economy. All of India's 1.4 billion people are exposed to unhealthy levels of ambient PM_{2.5}—the most harmful pollutant—emanating from multiple sources. Over half of PM_{2.5} emissions in India are formed in a “secondary” way in the upper atmosphere when different types of gaseous pollutants from one area, such as ammonia (NH₃), mix with other gaseous contaminants like sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) from another place. Agriculture, industry, power plants, households, and transport all contribute significantly to the formation of secondary PM_{2.5}. This secondary form spreads farther and wider than primary PM_{2.5}, traveling across states and cities and crossing jurisdictional borders. The air pollution challenge in India is therefore inherently multi-sectoral and multi-jurisdictional, requiring an “air-shed” approach.

This study examines air pollution control initiatives adopted by the states of Maharashtra and Punjab. This study is based entirely on secondary data sources. Data will be collected from the published data from the Pollution Control Boards of both Maharashtra and Punjab.

The overall picture for Maharashtra reveals that the most common underlying causes of the rising PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x, SO₂ and CO are the large number of vehicles, industrial emissions, construction and road dust, burning of wastes, etc.

Thane and Mumbai have recorded high levels of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels owing to the constant construction activity, industrial emissions and vehicular smoke.

Farmers burning crop residue, especially in districts like Ludhiana, Jalandhar and Amritsar, is a major contributor to air pollution. This burning of stubble lowers the air quality not only locally but also regionally.

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INTRODUCTION

Globally, air pollution is a silent killer. Air pollution levels in India are among the highest in the world, posing a significant threat to the country's health and economy. All of India's 1.4 billion people are exposed to unhealthy levels of ambient PM_{2.5} - the most harmful pollutant emanating from multiple sources. These small particulates with a diameter of less than 2.5 microns are about one-thirtieth the width of a human hair. Exposure to PM_{2.5} can cause such deadly illnesses as lung cancer, stroke, and heart disease. 1.67 million deaths in India in 2019 were attributable to air pollution, accounting for 17.8% of the country's total deaths. The health impacts of pollution also impose a high economic cost. Lost output from premature deaths and morbidity attributable to air pollution accounted for financial losses of US\$28.8 billion and \$8 billion, respectively, in India in 2019. This total loss of \$36.8 billion was 1.36% of India's gross domestic product (GDP).

PM_{2.5} comes from a variety of sources. Some of the most common sources include emissions from burning fossil fuels, such as coal or oil, and from biomass, such as wood, charcoal, or crop residues. PM_{2.5} can also come from windblown dust, including natural dust and dust from construction sites, roads, industrial plants, and even war-afflicted areas.

Over half of PM_{2.5} emissions in India are formed in a “secondary” way in the upper atmosphere when different types of gaseous pollutants from one area, such as ammonia (NH₃), mix with other gaseous contaminants like sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) from another place. Agriculture, industry, power plants, households, and transport all contribute significantly to the formation of secondary PM_{2.5}. This secondary form spreads farther and wider than primary PM_{2.5}, traveling across states and cities and crossing jurisdictional borders; and this is a significant cause of concern.

The air pollution challenge in India is therefore inherently multi-sectoral and multi-jurisdictional, requiring an “air-shed” approach. An air-shed is a region that shares a typical flow of air, which may become uniformly polluted and stagnant. Air quality within an air-shed largely depends on all the point and non-point sources of pollution within it. Since the formation of secondary particles and the transport of primary and secondary particles occur over large geographic areas, air sheds can extend over several hundred kilometers, well beyond the boundaries of cities. Air shed Management is fundamentally about protecting air quality within a defined area to safeguard health and the environment from the detrimental effect of pollution.

India, therefore, needs to look beyond its cities and take action at the sub-national level to develop effective air pollution control strategies and to apply a new set of tools for air-shed-based management. Standardizing tools across India is essential so that control strategies and relevant data sets can be linked.

A study of air quality for the entire country would entail drawing information about ambient

parameters along with wind patterns and other meteorological parameters from very large number of sources to get an idea about the air-sheds and can be considered a topic for a major research project. Therefore, this research paper will focus on two states – Punjab and Maharashtra. Both states are economically progressive, with strong foundations and a combination of agriculture and manufacturing.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

As per the ‘World Air Quality report-2019’ on the basis of particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), India ranks the fifth most polluted country in the world and dominates the list of the smoggiest urban areas, where 21 of the top 30 most polluted cities are in India (IQAir, 2019). Owing to increasing industrialization across the country, progressive worsening of ambient air pollution remains a great challenge for sustainable development and public health reforms (Gordon *et al.*, 2018).

In 2022, the World Health Organization (WHO) reported that air pollution was responsible for millions of deaths globally, with a significant portion attributed to ambient (outdoor) and household air pollution and that more than 99% of the global population lives in areas where air quality exceeds WHO guidelines.

At the recent India Clean Air Summit (ICAS) in Bengaluru, hosted by the Center for Study of Science, Technology and Policy (CSTEP), Ashish Tiwari, the top environment officer of Uttar Pradesh, recommended that NCAP adopt the airshed approach instead of the city-centric approach. According to the World Health Organization, low- and middle-income countries bear a disproportionate share of the air pollution burden, with 89% of premature deaths from outdoor air pollution occurring in these areas.

East Asia and the Pacific region, and South Asia, have particularly high population exposure to unsafe PM_{2.5} concentrations. While, India, China, Nigeria, and the Democratic Republic of Congo have some of the highest numbers of people living in extreme poverty and exposed to unsafe PM_{2.5} levels.

Kumar R. *et al.* (2015) concluded that the association between air quality in Ludhiana, Punjab, as indicated by visibility (haze), and daily mortality was statistically significant.

For every 1 km decrease in visibility at midday, mortality due to natural causes increased by 2.4%.

Gupta S. *et al.* (2013) found a significant correlation between air pollution and respiratory, cardiovascular, skin, and TB diseases in both the urban areas of Mandi Gobindgarh and the nearby rural areas. The effect of pollution is more pronounced in the metropolitan regions of Mandi Gobindgarh. One in every ten persons is affected by one of these diseases mentioned above.

Kumar *et al.* (2012) found that the total annual welfare loss in terms of health damages from air pollution caused by the burning of rice straw in rural Punjab amounts to 76 million.

AIM OF THE STUDY

This study aims to assess the air pollution control initiatives adopted by the states of Maharashtra and Punjab. Maharashtra is a state in western peninsular region of India and is the third most populated state of the country. Maharashtra's economy is driven by diverse industries including automotive, textiles, pharmaceuticals, petrochemicals, plastics, metal, cement, heavy chemicals, food processing, etc. Punjab is located in the North-western part of India with a much smaller geographical area as compared to Maharashtra. The geographical area of Maharashtra being 308,000 square kilometres. Whereas, the geographical area of Punjab is 50,362 square kilometers, and in comparison, much smaller than Maharashtra. Punjab's main industry is agriculture, which forms the backbone of its economy and makes it the "Bread Basket of India". Punjab also boasts of a strong manufacturing sector, with key industries including agro-based products, textiles, food processing, agriculture, sports equipment, electrical goods, etc.

While Maharashtra has a population of approximately 128.66 million (12.87 crore) and ranks third among states, Punjab has a population of about 31.19 million (3.12 crore), ranking 16th. It is well known that, although Punjab's population is smaller than Maharashtra's, the pollution from stubble burning in Punjab causes a severe AQI problem in the neighbouring state of Delhi.

An attempt is also being made to recommend methods that could serve as ideal approaches to achieving clean air in both states.

METHODOLOGY

This study is based entirely on secondary data sources. Data is collected from the Pollution Control Boards of both Maharashtra and Punjab and analyzed to understand the efforts being taken to control air pollution. An attempt is made to understand what extra measures can be adopted to address the poor AQI in North India especially in the neighbouring Union Territory of Delhi that has become the talk of the nation.

OBSERVATIONS:

i) MAHARASHTRA

Air pollution is a major issue in Maharashtra, especially in cities like Mumbai, Navi Mumbai, Thane, and Pune. The Mumbai Metropolitan Region (MMR) covers 18 municipal corporations and councils, a nagarpanchayat, and several villages.

The state's air quality has worsened with the onset of winter, with fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) exceeding permissible limits in over half of the state's cities. The overall picture for Maharashtra reveals that the most common underlying causes of the rising PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x, SO₂ and CO are the large number of vehicles, industrial emissions, construction and road dust, burning of wastes, etc. The pollutant levels, especially NO_x and SO₂ rise steeply in the MIDC areas while the city centres are ridden with very high levels of particulate matter – both PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. For instance, the Navi

Mumbai MIDC area recorded an average PM_{2.5} level of 37 µg/m³ and a PM₁₀ level of 102 µg/m³, a 100% increase compared to 2019-20. Thane and Mumbai have recorded high levels of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels owing to the constant construction activity, industrial emissions and vehicular smoke. An excessive number of vehicles in major cities has contributed to traffic congestion and the consequent rise in vehicular exhaust from increased idling at traffic bottlenecks. Dependence on private vehicles is also a significant issue that needs to be tackled through proper urban planning and the provision of effective public transport for the residents.

The Maharashtra Pollution Control Board (MPCB) is taking steps to address air pollution, including stricter enforcement of pollution-control measures and awareness campaigns.

The regulations are explicitly prescribed for separate fields such as construction sites, ready-mix concrete plants, industries, and the transport sector.

As construction activities and the transport sector are the chief sources of air pollution in most major cities of Maharashtra, several measures are in place. Some key initiatives adopted at construction sites include mandatory dust control measures for construction projects over 50 mts, including 25-foot dust curtains, bus-mounted water sprinklers, and strict regulations for vehicles transporting construction materials. Existing captive Ready-Mix Concrete (RMC) projects must transition to fully enclosed setups and they should be located at least 200m away from schools, colleges, hospitals and courts. These RMC plants must operate within the permissible emission limit and follow noise-control arrangements.

The MPCB also has regulations in place for the transport sector to control pollution, although the Transport Department is responsible for addressing automobile/vehicle pollution. The MPCB, along with the Ministry of Environment & Forests & Climate Change, Government of India, has prescribed emission standards for pollution control. Regular PUC checks are mandatory for vehicles to ensure they meet emission standards. Vehicle owners must comply with these standards, and those found in violation are penalized. Citizens can report complaints about vehicle pollution to the Transport Department or MPCB.

Enforcement and Monitoring are the responsibility of special squads that ensure compliance and impose penalties for non-compliance, including stop-work orders and site sealing.

Apart from this, MPCB has set up real-time air quality monitoring stations across Mumbai and Pune to track pollution levels. Mobile monitoring vans patrol the cities to monitor air quality on the go. Industries are required to follow emission standards and implement pollution control measures. MPCB also runs awareness campaigns to educate citizens about air pollution and its effects.

They encourage public participation in air quality monitoring and reporting pollution incidents and collaborate with other government agencies, NGOs, and other stakeholders to tackle

air pollution. They have also implemented Graded Response Action Plan (GRAP), which takes action based on air quality levels. All these measures aim to improve air quality and public health in Maharashtra's urban areas.

While cities such as Mumbai, Thane, Mira-Bhayandar, and Navi Mumbai within MMR have each taken steps to reduce dust from construction sites and vehicle emissions, these scattered efforts lack the comprehensive planning, resources, and data sharing needed to make a large-scale impact.

ii) PUNJAB

Punjab, predominantly an agrarian state, is also well-known for its industrialization in the post-independence era. The tremendous number of industrial processes that began led to a much stronger economy. The majority of these industries depend on coal to meet their energy requirement. This, in turn, led to a decline in the State's air quality.

Punjab faces a serious air pollution problem, especially during the winter months. Farmers burning crop residue, especially in districts like Ludhiana, Jalandhar and Amritsar, is a major contributor to air pollution. This burning of stubble lowers the air quality not only locally but also regionally.

Urban and peri-urban PM comes mainly from vehicular emissions, road dust, construction, industrial clusters, waste burning, and small-scale biomass use. Paddy stubble burning is an acute seasonal source that spikes PM levels in October-November, aggravating downwind AQI in Punjab and adjoining regions.

Thermal power plants, brick kilns and other large point sources add to the PM and NO_x/Sox, especially where emission norms or biomass co-firing targets are not fully met.

On the other hand, emissions from the existing power plants, industrial processes, and vehicles have also been constantly increasing. Construction activities and road dust have also contributed to the pollutant load. Spraying chemical pesticides and insecticides adds a significant source of dangerous pollutants to the air. Thus making the air a complex mixture of particulate matter, SO₂, NO_x and Ammonia. All this is affecting the health and well-being of its residents, with respiratory problems and cardiovascular diseases on the rise, as well as the harm to crops, soil, and water bodies. Thus impacting the State's ecosystem.

The Pollution Control Board of Punjab (PPCB) is tackling air pollution through a mix of monitoring, regulation, sector-specific plans (especially stubble burning and industry); and public campaigns to change-on-ground practices. The Board's recent focus areas include elimination open burning of waste, managing crop residue smoke, tightening industrial emissions and improving data and planning capacity. In an attempt to create awareness, PPCB has deployed a mobile air quality monitoring van that travels across districts, compares pollution levels between green and polluted sites; and acts as a 'moving classroom' to explain air quality and mitigation options to citizens. It has

also implemented the State’s Action Plan to eliminate paddy stubble burning, coordinated with CAQM. Along with the State Agriculture Department, PPCB supports large-scale crop residue management: subsidized in-situ and ex-situ machinery, promotion of bio-decomposers, and linking straw to industry to reduce farm-fire smoke.

It has installed and operates pollution-control equipment and online continuous-emission monitoring systems. It is involved in measures on vehicular and road-dust emissions such as phasing out old/diesel vehicles, apart from the other stringent measures against non-compliant vehicles.

Figure 1. Physiographic Map of India

CONCLUSION

Rapid urbanization and the consequent increase in energy consumption and vehicular traffic, the lack of city-planning principles in newly expanding towns and cities, coupled with excessive population, pose a challenging premise for the existing issues of poor AQI, which are ultimately responsible for the citizens' poor health.

Maharashtra's geographical area is six times that of Punjab. But stubble burning in Punjab has a more profound impact on the air quality of neighbouring regions. The air pollution challenge in

India is therefore inherently multi-sectoral and multi-jurisdictional, and the need for an “airshed” approach is clearly justified. Given the concept of airshed for the transmission of pollutants over large geographical areas, the case is valid in the context of the poor AQI experienced in Delhi and the neighbouring NCR. No doubt, the sources of pollution in New Delhi are several. But its peculiar geographical positioning and the prevalence of the westerly winds, coupled with smoke from the stubble burning, all add to the problem faced by the air-shed region that encompasses the North Indian states of Punjab, Haryana, and Delhi.

The geographical location of the Himalayan ranges along the Northern fringe of Delhi and Punjab serves as a barrier, preventing the dispersal of pollutants in the region. In contrast, Maharashtra has a comparatively advantageous location, owing to its coastal setting, which facilitates the dispersal of air pollutants. However, in winter, wind speeds are often low and wind patterns shift, allowing them to accumulate near the surface. The prevalence of temperature inversions prevents mixing of air and traps pollutants in the lower atmosphere for extended periods. Apart from this broader climate, patterns such as early onset of La Nina conditions have partially altered the usual strong wind reversal from across the sea. This contributes to air stagnation. These combined factors have pushed Mumbai’s air quality into ‘poor’ and ‘very poor’ categories, leading to health risks and the implementation of mitigation measures by the municipal corporation. Both the MPCB as well as PPCB is taking steps to address air pollution. Still, it's a collective responsibility. Citizens, industries, and government agencies need to work together to reduce pollution and create a healthier environment.

Key initiatives taken by PPCB include a blanket ban on open burning of waste across the State. It also emphasizes the need for promoting composting and mulching of horticultural waste. The PPCB is engaging in Capacity building by working with Urban Local Bodies, Resident Welfare Associations, and NGOs to promote community-level solutions for sustainable waste management. The PPCB has also convinced some major polluting industries to switch to cleaner fuels such as CNG/RLNG.

They're running awareness campaigns to educate citizens about the importance of reducing air pollution and promoting sustainable practices.

These measures aim to reduce air pollution, improve public health, and promote a cleaner environment in Punjab. Reducing high AQI in Punjab needs a multi-sector strategy that simultaneously cuts emissions from agriculture, transport, industry, waste burning and dust, while strengthening monitoring and enforcement. In addition to having city action plans, Punjab is also part of the National Clean Air Programme.

Consequently, a cleaner environment in Punjab will lead to a favourable AQI in the entire airshed area that is located in North India.

Maharashtra's air pollution control measures include construction site regulations (water sprinkling, covering materials), road dust control (mechanical sweeping, water sprinkling, anti-smog guns), vehicular emission control (promoting public transport and carpooling, strict enforcement), and industrial controls (emission standards, cleaner technology, air pollution control devices). The state also focuses on increasing green cover through tree plantation and green belts, and on implementing cleaner energy initiatives, such as promoting electric vehicles and solar power.

Use of cleaner technologies, such as electric crematoriums, solar water heaters, and dry fly ash handling systems. Mass transit with a lower carbon footprint, improved city planning, traffic management and enforcing stricter emission norms for vehicles.

Green initiatives such as developing green corridors, urban green belts, vertical gardens, etc., and environmentally friendly waste management practices should be adopted aggressively.

It is necessary to expand and modernize the air quality monitoring network (CAAQMS plus low-cost sensors), integrate data into public dashboards and early-warning systems, and use CEPI/NCAP indicators as triggers for corrective action.

Strengthening inter-departmental coordination (agriculture, transport, urban, power, and health) and city-level clean air cells, drawing on multi-sectoral plans such as the Amritsar 2025-2030 air pollution mitigation plan, is essential.

Implementation of the State Action Plan on Climate Change and Human Health by linking AQI alerts to health advisories, hospital preparedness, and targeted protection of vulnerable groups. Lastly, Mumbai's airshed region has not been scientifically defined and requires comprehensive study. Some studies suggest the existence of a 'western airshed'. This encompassing MMR, Pune and parts of Gujarat. A World Bank study suggests dividing India into six broad airsheds, but these definitions remain preliminary too. An airshed-level management body for MMR could take the lead in conducting detailed research to accurately delineate Mumbai's airshed region.

Such an entity could further strengthen collaboration among key stakeholders — government agencies, industry players and civil society. It can help identify and understand the urban and rural areas that constitute the larger airshed of the region, facilitate shared infrastructure development, expand data collection and monitoring, and streamline policymaking.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Urbanization, though a universal issue, necessitates the adoption of specific measures to make it sustainable ecologically. It

Combating air pollution is a complex task requiring coordinated efforts from all stakeholders. The most critical challenge that hinders air pollution in India is the lack of enforcement, the lack of stringent air pollution standards, and reliance on country-specific guidelines that are way higher than

the WHO-recommended guidelines. Therefore, ensuring implementation of the existing plans and policies is essential.

Apart from that, designing buildings and city layouts to enhance wind flow and ventilation corridors allows pollutants to disperse freely and effectively. Construction activities should be strictly monitored so that PM levels can be kept under control. Reflective and permeable materials must be used for roofs and pavements to counter urban heat islands, which worsen inversion effects.

Use of technology like drones to identify pollution hot spots and potentially disperse pollutants through the use of anti-smog guns, etc. Susceptible individuals should use air purifiers equipped with HEPA (High Efficiency Particulate Air) filters and activated carbon to improve indoor air. Adopting electric vehicles and hydrogen fuel as alternatives to traditional gasoline, two-stroke, and diesel vehicles can significantly reduce vehicular emissions in urban areas.

Incentivize cycling and walking and simultaneously upgrade infrastructure accordingly.

Temporary closure of fuel stations, brick kilns, and construction activity to contain the critical situation arising out of poor ambient air quality.

Occasional lockdowns or Work-from-Home should be the norm during high AQI episodes to safeguard citizens' health.

Planting trees while maintaining the existing forest cover is an undeniable option available to mankind. This is essentially the most critical solution to most problems faced by the developing countries. With its growing population, rapid and reckless urbanization, and a heavy reliance on private vehicles, Indian states need to work aggressively to achieve sustainability across all sectors and fields.

Punjab and Maharashtra have some of the most densely populated cities. Creating new growth pole centers in less populated areas might help reduce the burden of air pollution faced by cities such as Ludhiana, Amritsar, and Jalandhar in Punjab, and Mumbai and Pune in Maharashtra.

Indian states need to adopt a multifaceted approach that combines stringent regulations, technological innovations, public awareness campaigns, and regional and international collaborations to address trans-boundary pollution issues.

Air pollution is not always experienced as occurring from Point Source Pollution. Air pollution in any part of the world can drift to the rest of the world under the influence of the prevailing winds. This itself proves that it is necessary to look at the issue holistically rather than treating it in isolation.

Improving air quality is a long-term effort that requires strong institutional frameworks, supported by both state and federal governments. Lasting progress can only be achieved through an airshed-based approach, with a clear mandate for integrated planning and coordinated action throughout the entire region.

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The logo for the journal, featuring the text "GOEIJR" in a large, stylized, orange-brown font. The letters are slightly shadowed and appear to be floating above a faint, light blue globe graphic that is partially visible behind the text.